

RELIABILITY OF THE STRENGTH AND FRACTURE PROCESS OF SiC/Al COMPOSITE WITH DIFFERENT INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH

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SUMMARY: The tensile test was carried out for unidirectional reinforced SiC/Al composite, which was fabricated by hot press and had different interfacial shear strengths. A Monte-Carlo simulation based on the elastic-plastic finite element method with interfacial layer around the fibers was performed. Effect of interfacial shear strength on composite strength and reliability was investigated. The results show that composite strength and Weibull shape parameter increase as the interfacial shear strength increases. The interfacial shear strength contribution to composite strength and reliability effectively is till near by the shear strength of the matrix. It is concluded that the strength and reliability is closely related to the fiber fracture process.

KEYWORDS: Fiber Reinforced Metals, SiC/Al Composite, Interfacial Shear Strength, Tensile Strength, Reliability, Monte-Carlo Simulation, Finite Element Method, Fracture Process.

INTRODUCTION

It is widely known that interfacial bonding strength in fiber reinforced metal matrix composites influences many mechanical behaviors of the composites as an important factor. Therefore, a lot of studies have been reported on controlling reaction in the interface[1-2], measuring interfacial strength[3-5], effect of interfacial strength or interface thickness on composite strength[6-10]. It has been pointed in studies of computer simulation that the strength of composite increases with increasing interfacial bonding strength and then remains nearly constant when the ductility of matrix is high[6]. The strength of composite is reduced with increasing thickness of reaction layer[7]. However, it has not been clear how the interfacial bonding strength influences the strength of composite, and reliability of the strength.

In this study, the tensile test was carried out for unidirectional reinforced SiC/Al composite fabricated by hot press with different interfacial shear strengths. Meanwhile, a Monte-Carlo simulation based on the elastic-plastic finite element method with interfacial layer around the fibers was built. Effect of interfacial shear strength on composite strength and reliability was discussed.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Matrix material in the present study was A1050 pure aluminum plate with a thickness of 0.3mm. SiC_{CVD} fiber, produced by Textron Specialty Materials (type SCS-2, diameter: 140.μm), was used as reinforcement material. Hot press was carried out in three processes to make the SiC/Al composites. Aluminum plate was cut into pieces (30.70mm²) which were then annealed at 300. for 30min in air. In order to arrange the fibers on the pieces orderly, U-shaped grooves with a 0.5mm interspace were made on one side of the aluminum pieces by pressing stainless steel wires (with a diameter of 140.μm) into the pieces. SiC fibers were put into the grooves on the surface of one aluminum piece, which was then overlapped by another aluminum piece. Hot press processes were carried out to make the SiC/Al composites. In addition, SiC/Al composites containing only one single fiber were fabricated for measuring the interfacial shear strength by multiple fracture method. Hot press was completed in three processes as shown in Table 1.

...Tensile tests were performed using a screw driven and constant crosshead speed tester (Shimadzu, AG-5000ES). All tensile tests were done at room temperature with a constant crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min and a gauge length 30mm. The load was recorded as a function of time using a load-time recorder.

Tensile specimens of SiC/Al composite were cut into 9mm in width and 70mm in length from the piece of SiC/Al composites, as there exist 13 SiC filaments in a tensile specimen. The fiber volume fraction is 4.0%. In order to examine the interfacial shear strength, single fiber specimens, where the single SiC fiber was located in the center, were cut into 9mm in width from SiC/Al composites. Further, to understand the fiber strength in the SiC/Al composites, the fibers were extracted by dissolving the matrix with 10%NaOH water solution, and then a tensile test was carried out for the fibers. Tabs of aluminum were set to both the ends of all tensile specimens. For each fabricating condition, the numbers of tensile specimens of SiC/Al composite, the single fiber composite and extracted SiC fibers were over 50, 30 and 50, respectively. Weibull distribution was used to evaluate the strength of composite and extracted SiC fiber.

Table 1 Hot press conditions.

Process number	I	II	III
Temperature (K)	773	873	893
Pressure (MPa)	28	47	56
Holding time (min)	10	20	40

MODEL AND TECHNIQUE OF THE SIMULATION

A Monte-Carlo simulation using the elastic-plastic finite element method for evaluating the tensile strength of the unidirectional SiC/Al composite has been performed. In the present simulation, interfacial elements are incorporated between the fiber and matrix elements in the model, which has been proposed in reference[11]. The finite element model and mesh in the present study are shown in Fig. 1. Two one-dimensional line elements representing the reinforcing fibers are incorporated into two sides along the y-axis of a 4-nodes isoparametric element (plane stress), which represents the metal matrix. Further, the interfacial layer represented by a 4-nodes isoparametric element having 1.μm width (plane stress) is incorporated between the fiber element and the matrix element. The model, having 13 fibers ($V_f= 4.0\%$), is divided into 30 elements along y-axis. Y-axis of nodes in the lower side is fixed, but displacement increment is given along y-axis in the upper side.

Weibull random numbers using the inverse function of Weibull distribution give the strength of fiber elements. Furthermore, for exactly evaluating each element stress increment necessary to the fiber break, the r_{min} method is applied to the simulation procedure[12]. The fiber is regarded as elastic state and the matrix is assumed to be elastic-plastic. Fiber element is considered to break when the stress, which is along the axial direction of the fiber, reaches

the strength of that fiber element. After a fiber element breaks, the stiffness will be changed to zero, and the axial load, which was loading on that fiber element, is decreased to zero by dividing the load into 20 times. Interface element is considered to be failure when the shear stress reaches the shear strength of the interface. Taking into the account of the friction after the interface break pointed by reference[13], a small stiffness (20MPa) is given to the interface element after an interface element breaks.

The present simulation was performed 50 times repeatedly for each interfacial shear strengths. Material parameters in the present simulation are shown in Table 2. Yield stress,

Fig.1 Finite element Model and mesh.

Table 2 Material constants used in the present simulation.

Elastic modulus of SiC fiber (GPa)	421.7
Weibull shape parameter of fiber strength	6.1
Weibull scale parameter of fiber strength (GPa)	4.8
Diameter of SiC fiber (mm)	0.14
Standard gauge length (mm)	30
Volume fraction of SiC fiber (%)	4.0
Elastic modulus of matrix (GPa)	70
Poisson's ratio of matrix	0.33
Work hardening coefficient of matrix (MPa)	88.6
Work hardening exponent of matrix	0.22
Yield stress of matrix (MPa)	30.6
Thickness of composite (mm)	0.6
Elastic modulus of interface element (GPa)	70
Poisson's ratio of interface element	0.33
Interfacial shear strength (MPa)	30,50,80

Fig.2 Flow chart of the present simulation.

work hardening coefficient and exponent of the matrix are obtained by a tensile test using specimens of the seam pure aluminum as the matrix of SiC/Al composite fabricated in this study. The flow chart of the present simulation is shown in Fig.2.

RESULTS

The Interfacial Shear Strength and Reliability of the Composite Strength

The interfacial shear strengths, obtained by multiple fracture method of single fiber SiC/Al are shown in Table 3. In this table, the average strength, Weibull shape and scale parameter of the extracted SiC fiber are listed too. Three SiC/Al composites with different interfacial shear strengths are prepared by different hot press processes. Fiber strength f_f and its scatter (Weibull shape parameter m) have almost not changed for each process. Fig.3 shows a stress-strain curve of SiC/Al composite (process III). From this figure, it can be seen that the slope of the curve has a change due to yielding of the matrix. Till the maximum stress (composite strength), there are abrupt changes of the stress at some times on the curve. The stress changes are considered to be owing to breaking of the fibers in the composite. In order to confirm the results obtained from the present simulation, in the case of interfacial shear strength of 30MPa, the strength and Weibull parameters of SiC/Al composite from both the experiment and simulation methods are listed in Table 4. Composite strength and Weibull shape parameter obtained from the simulation are almost in agreement with those from the experiment. It indicates that the present simulation is applicable.

Table 3 Interfacial shear strength and extracted fiber strength.

Process number	I	II	III	
Interfacial shear strength (MPa)	10.9	24.7	30.2	
Extracted fiber	f_f (GPa)	4.1	4.4	4.4
	m	6.0	7.7	6.1
	fD_0 (GPa)	4.5	4.7	4.8

Fig.3 A stress-strain curve of SiC/Al composite (process III).

Table 4 Strength and Weibull parameters of SiC/Al composite from the experiment and simulation.

Method	Interfacial shear strength (MPa)	Sample number	Fiber volume fraction (%)	Average strength (MPa)	Weibull parameters		
					m	fD_0 (MPa)	C.V.(%)
Experiment	30.2	41	4.0	203.2	16.8	209.6	6.6
Simulation	30.0	50	4.0	215.9	17.2	232.6	6.7

The strength and Weibull shape parameter obtained from the two methods are shown in Fig.4. Both composite strength and Weibull shape parameter increase greatly as the interfacial

Fig.4 The interfacial shear strength vs strength and Weibull parameter of composite.

shear strength increases, until the interfacial shear strength approaching to the shear strength of aluminum matrix (about 40MPa). But when the interfacial shear strength surpasses the matrix shear strength, their enhancement becomes slow. It implies that the interfacial shear strength contributes to composite strength and reliability greatly only when interfacial bonding strength is lower than the matrix shear strength.

To examine the contribution of the interfacial shear strength to the composite strength, composite strength σ_c obtained from the two methods has been compared with the calculation strength σ_{rom} by the rule of mixture (ROM) as follows.

$$\sigma_{rom} = \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad \dots\dots (1)$$

Where, σ_f is the fiber strength, V_f is fiber volume fraction (4.0%) and σ_m corresponds to the matrix stress when the composite breaks. In the present study, the strength of extracted fiber shown in Table 3 is used as σ_f , the strength of pure aluminum (58MPa) is used as σ_m . The relationship between σ_c / σ_{rom} and interfacial shear strength is shown in Fig.5. It can

Fig.5 Interfacial shear strength vs σ_c / σ_{rom} .

be seen that σ_c / σ_{rom} goes up as interfacial shear strength increases. It means that the composite strength becomes near to its maximum value if the interface is strong enough. When interfacial shear strength approaches to the shear strength of the matrix (about 40MPa), composite strength reaches to its maximum, that is, the value calculated by ROM. It is suggested that the contribution of the interfacial shear strength for the composite strength has a limitation, which is near the shear strength of the matrix.

The Strength Reliability and Structure Process of the Composite

It can be considered that the weak fibers will break at first, comparing with the strong ones during loading in the composite. Till the maximum stress, some breaking of the fiber in the composite will happen during tensile test as shown in Fig.3. The relationship between the strength, reliability of the composite and the fracture process has been discussed in the present study. By calculating average number of the accumulated broken fiber after reading out the counts of breaking fiber from stress-strain curves, relationship between average broken fiber count and the strength, Weibull shape parameter are shown in Fig. 6, respectively. The strength and Weibull shape parameter go up along with the average count of broken fiber. It hints that the strength and reliability of the composite relate with the accumulation of the fiber breaking in the composite.

Fig.6 Average count of broken fiber in SiC/Al composite vs the composite strength and Weibull shape parameter.

Fig.7 Number of broken fiber vs fiber stress and Weibull shape parameter.

Further, in order to discuss the effect of the accumulation of fiber breaking, the stress of the composite has been read out when the fiber break in breaking fiber order for all specimens. Then the fiber stress and Weibull shape parameter have been calculated by ROM as shown in equation (1) and Weibull distribution, respectively. Fig.7 shows the number of broken fiber and the corresponding fiber stress and Weibull shape parameter. The fiber stress and Weibull shape parameter increase with number of broken fiber for each hot press process. That is, the more the accumulating fiber fracture is, the higher fiber stress needed for the fracture is, and the lower the fiber stress scatter is. Therefore, the more the accumulating fiber fracture is, it becomes more obvious that composite strength is controlled by the fiber which has a high strength and low strength scatter. From the results mentioned above, it is clarified that composite strength and reliability are related closely with the accumulation of breaking fiber.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study shows that composite strength and Weibull shape parameter increase as the interfacial shear strength increases. The interfacial shear strength contributes to composite strength and reliability effectively is till near by the shear strength of the matrix. It is concluded that the composite strength and reliability is closely related to the fiber fracture process.

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